

THE USE OF ANALYTICAL TOOLS IN RESHAPING THE SHOPPING EXPERIENCE OF THE FUTURE

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: The goal of the research was to discover the key metrics needed to shape next-generation retailing in India using predictive analytics.

Design/Research Methodology/approach: The aims of the research study were investigated using factor analysis.

Findings: The article emphasises the importance of merchants adopting a new approach to keep their customers for extended periods of time. Providing customers with a product or service has become almost a commodity. In order to fully satisfy their customers, retailers are expected to step up their game in the ever-growing retail market.

Research Implications: In order to fully satisfy their customers, retailers are expected to step raise their efforts in the ever-growing retail market.

Scope for future work / Research limitations: Consumer transformation has indeed begun to have a significant impact on the future of retailing in India. As a result, retailers must adopt a strategy to understand what their customers want from them in relation to their product or service, and delicate their processes more effectively.

Originality/value: The majority of research on predictive analytics or big data analytics has focused on the value of their application in the retail business. As a result, the focus of this research is to investigate the core aspects identified with the help of predictive analytics that the retail business must embrace in order to thrive during times of dynamic layout.

Keywords: Retailing, span of time, retailers, shopping pattern

Paper Type: Research Paper

INTRODUCTION

The retail industry in India is undergoing a metamorphosis, and this rising market's growth pattern is changing dramatically. Providing better products and services, being imaginative and creative in reaching out to customers, and making shopping more accessible and viable to all are some of the key characteristics that have contributed to the retail industry's recent exponential rise. The retail business is in a position where it needs to explore new prospects for the benefit of the consumers shopping experience, propelled by radical alteration in

dynamic trends, ever rising need for diversity, lifestyle, and spending patterns. Retailers must be futuristic (Srini R Srinivasan & Rajesh Srivatsava, 2010) and combine variances from several dimensions in order to gain customer-level awareness.

Technology is something that marketing geniuses lavish on in the retail industry (Dan Hopping, 2000). Incorporating current trends into your strategy is one thing to consider, as it will eventually help you stand out from the competition. However, if merchants want to stay in business in the long run, they must do more than merely keep up with the current trend. To keep not only their customers, but also their place in the market, they must think ahead of their competitors and assess what the public expects from them.

With this in mind, a study was carried out to discover the many metrics that will aid in the design of next-generation retailing in India via predictive analytics. For the objective of gathering primary data, a well-structured questionnaire was developed. The study used a convenience sampling method with a sample size of 100 people. The gathered answers were loaded into the statistical package for social science (SPSS) ver.20.0 for the actual view of the study, and the quantitative analysis was done with the goal of arriving at a conclusion with respect to the framed objective.

There are a variety of strategies that can be used to detect potential consumer demands. Predictive analysis is one such effective instrument or measurement. It is a more proactive method in which historical and current data are acquired and analysed in order to foresee the future prospects of their firm and act appropriately in order to stay ahead of the curve, compete effectively, and gain a significant amount of market share.

It's past time for merchants to start focusing on the various benefits they may offer in addition to their product or service. The retail industry is fiercely competitive, and the only way to set one company apart from the rest is to offer additional services. This research primarily focuses on identifying the amenities that consumers demand from stores and assisting shops in supplying those amenities so that they can stay in business for a longer period of time.

Many research on subjects relating to predictive analytics or big data analytics in the retail industry have been undertaken in the past. The following are a few examples of such research undertaken by various academics.

Eric T. Bradlow et al. (2017) conducted research on 'The role of big data and predictive analytics in retailing,' in which they looked at the opportunities and possibilities of big data in retailing, as well as the importance of predictive analytics in forming a strong retail base for new initiatives. They also discussed the ethical and privacy concerns that may develop as a result of the use of big data in retailing in their study.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A further study, undertaken by Hamza Belarbi et al. (2016), looked into the importance of predictive analytics in the retail industry. They concentrated mostly on the value provided by big data in the retail industry. They also mentioned that predictive analytics is not limited to a single business, but can be adopted and applied in the retail industry as well.

In a study conducted by SabyasachiChakraborty and KashyapBarua (2017), it was discovered that big data analytics aids retail sectors in improving their customers' experiences and making timely and correct judgments about product sales. It was also stressed that retail industries can understand when, where, and why consumers buy using big data analytics.

Predictive analytics, according to SandeepPuri, VineetSehgal, and Vivek Sharma (2013), helps retailers understand their operations and respond quickly to changing market patterns. They also stated emphatically that predictive analytics provides merchants with data that they can use to differentiate themselves from their market competitors.

According to Mathew Ridge, Kevin Allan Johnston, and Brain O'Donovan (2015), the use of big data analytics in South Africa is primarily focused on technical algorithms and systems development, with little industry-specific predictive analytics.

Venky Shankar (2019) mentioned that statistical econometrics and data science models can be created with the goal of making the best decision possible.

The study also looked at how machine learning and artificial intelligence are employed in predictive analytics, and how they might serve as an underpinning for efficient decision.

The majority of studies on predictive analytics or big data analytics has focused on the importance of their use in the retail industry or the vital part they played in assisting retailers to keep up with their customers. However, there appears to be a dearth of research focusing on the components identified by predictive analytics that the retail industry must adopt in order to cope with the volatile market environment. As a result, the focus of this research is to investigate the core aspects identified with the help of predictive analytics that the retail business must embrace in order to thrive in times of dynamic layout.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The aims of the research work were investigated using factor analysis. The results of the detailed analysis, as well as their interpretations, are listed below. The goal of the study was to identify the many metrics that should be considered while building next-generation retailing in India in order for the industry to grow.

To achieve this goal, the internal consistency (Chelsea Goforth, 2015) of the variables used in the study was measured using Cronbach's alpha and KMO Bartlett's test on SPSS.

Cronbach's Alpha - Table.1 reveals that the 17 items adopted in this research have a reliability level of 0.814, suggesting that the items have a higher level of internal consistency and are thus suitable for use in the study..

**Table 1. Cronbach's Alpha as a reliability tool to validate the data
Reliability Statistics**

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.814	17

Table.2 shows that all the variables are significant statistically at the.05 level, as well as indicating that the variables are adequate for categorical data, as the KMO value produced is.739.

Table 2. KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.739
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	327.421
	df	136
	Sig.	.000

The tool was used to define the desired objective because the variables were both dependable and acceptable for conducting factor analysis.

Table 3 displays the four extracted factors, all of which have an eigen value greater than one. A total of 17 variables were reduced to four primary elements, as can be seen.

Table 3. Total Variance Explained

Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings	
Tota	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance
3.323	19.545	19.545	3.323	19.545	19.545	2.859	16.818
2.121	12.476	32.022	2.121	12.476	32.022	2.129	12.524
1.757	10.337	42.359	1.757	10.337	42.359	1.929	11.344
1.588	9.344	51.703	1.588	9.344	51.703	1.873	11.016

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

The rotated component matrix (Table 4) depicts the four primary types of metrics that must be considered when building India's next-generation retailing. The first set of categories is aptly named LOYALTY PROGRAM, in which customers are supposed to receive discounts and rebates, prizes, free items, and access to events and new releases, among other things. EXTENDED REALITY is the second category, in which consumers should be provided with virtual experiences such as 3D visualisation reality, hyper-personalization, extraordinary online interfaces, and mobile applications.

Table 4. Rotated Component Matrix^a

Additional amenities	Components			
	1	2	3	4
Automated order fulfilment	.752			
Discounts & Rebates	.621			
Free merchandises	.579			
Access to events, releases etc.	.591			
Rewards	.562			
Website interface design		.698		
Availability of mobile applications		.582		
3D Visual reality		.571		
Hyper- Personalisation		.512		
Remote Delivery/Shipping			.657	
Free installation service			.539	
Extended warranty			.532	
Varied financial options			.371	
In-depth product assortments				.772
Prompt service recovery				.641
Good complaint handling process				.598
Drop ship model availability				.541

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization

- a. Rotation converged in 9 iterations.

Consumers expect perks such as remote shipping/delivery, free installation assistance, extended warranty, and a variety of financial alternatives under the third set of metrics, which can be labelled AUGMENTED CONTINUUM. The fourth set of metrics is known as HEURISTIC MEASURES, and it includes extra features like quick service recovery, extensive product assortments, a good complaint management method, and the availability of a drop ship model. These are the four metrics that can be used to shape next-generation retailing in India in order to provide consumers with exceptional experiences in addition to the usual services.

DISCUSSIONS

The ever-increasing demographic reward populace (ShekarAiyar&AshokaMody, 2011), income rates, earnings distributions, expenditures, and the millennial workforce have all contributed to a good trend for India's retaining industry. Over the last decade, India's population has gradually evolved into a more sophisticated lifestyle, with sky-high needs,

desires, and expectations. Before acquiring a product or service, people no longer only look at it.

Selling a high-quality product or service isn't enough to keep a retail firm afloat in today's market (Martin J. Burger, Evert J. Meijers & Frank G. Van Oort, 2014). Every merchant must supply extra features that will give them a competitive edge over competitors selling the same goods or service.

The research identified primary categories of metrics, each of which includes a variety of amenities that are anticipated to be offered by merchants alongside their products or services from the perspective of the consumers. The future of commerce in India is already being shaped by consumer development. As a result, retailers must take proactive steps to learn what their customers want from them in addition to their product or service, and fine-tune their processes accordingly.

CONCLUSION

The retailing business in India has undergone significant changes in numerous facets over the years. It is undeniably one of India's most dynamic and fast-paced sectors, having gone through a variety of phases. Consumers, like the industry, have been evolving in terms of their spending habits, income, taste, and preferences, among other things (Alladi Venkatesh, 1994). Consumers are more accessible to a variety of international goods and services as a result of globalisation and internationalisation, which has influenced their degree of expectation (Gabriela Hanus, 2018). Consumers' expectations of a shop have entirely evolved, and they no longer want to buy a product but instead want to be taken on a relaxing journey and have a pleasant buying experience. Consumers want to improve not only their buying experience, but also their ability to make the best purchase decision possible. Retailers must have a thorough understanding of their customers' profiles in order to provide exactly what they desire.

Having a look at the rate at which the Indian retail industry is growing, it is clear that the future holds a very exciting and rewarding period for all stakeholders in the retail industry, offered they make the appropriate amendments and incorporate all of the elements that consumers consider into their operations.

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